

Uplifting High Performance of Non-education Graduate: An Explanatory Sequential Mixed Method Design

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Abstract. The purpose of this study was to identify the quantitative aspects that require further explanation regarding the performance of non-educational graduate teachers. Additionally, it aims to assess the level of job satisfaction. Furthermore, to investigate the significant relationship between the variables mentioned, and ultimately, to determine the school program that can develop high performance in non-educational graduate teachers to enhance job satisfaction. A total of 90 non-educational graduate teachers from the Tagum North District were identified as respondents using the formula by Tabachnick and Fidell. At the same time, an additional five participants were selected through purposive sampling for the qualitative findings. The study utilized an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design. Two methods for collecting the data were utilized. For the quantitative phase, the researcher used a survey questionnaire. Furthermore, in the qualitative phase, the researcher used in-depth interviews to gather the data. According to the quantitative analysis, a significant relationship exists between the performance of non-education graduate teachers and their job satisfaction. In addition, the quantitative findings were followed up by the qualitative findings. Thus, it was found that the school program to develop high performance of non-education graduate teachers to boost job satisfaction of teachers revealed four major themes, namely: (1) self-learning and being resourceful, (2) seeking help, (3) openness and acceptance, and (4) avoiding run-of-the-mill instruction.

KEY WORDS

1. Non-education graduate 2. job satisfaction 3. explanatory sequential design 4. teachers 5. Tagum North Division 6. Philippines

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1. Introduction

Given the rapidly growing student population and the establishment of new educational institutions in remote regions, the Department of Education must recruit additional educators to meet the increasing demand. Teachers in public schools in the Philippines are the third-best-paid profession relative to other occupations. While other professionals traveled abroad, others were accumulating educational credits, undertaking the Licensure Examination for Teachers, and submitting applications to the Department of Education. Nonetheless, non-education degree teachers employed in public schools may encounter specific problems and difficulties. Insufficient pedagogical development, inadequate classroom management skills, challenges in accommodating diverse learning styles, limited proficiency in technology-based instruction, ad-

ministrative issues, and a need for ongoing professional growth are some of the challenges faced by newly graduated education teachers.

In the United States, Ingersoll and Curran (2019) reported that 17 to 22 percent of fundamental courses were taught by instructors lacking degrees in education or relevant topic certifications. Specifically, in the United States, approximately one-fifth of public-school pupils from grades 7-12, totaling around 4,310,000 out of 20,700,000, were instructed by educators lacking at least a minor in English, Literature, Communication, Speech, Journalism and Mass Communication, English Education, or Reading Education. This affects the pupils' learning.

In the Philippines, individuals working in any field, including those with non-education degrees, may encounter difficulties in executing their duties. Teaching is a challenging and demanding career, with numerous variables contributing to job dissatisfaction. They may encompass a deficiency in supplies, which includes insufficient teaching materials, obsolete textbooks, and a deficiency of technology tools, which might exacerbate educators' striving to deliver optimal instruction for their students (Tarraya, 2023).

Further, in the national context. A study by Mary Ann Ching (2022) examined the job satisfaction and performance of non-education graduate teachers in the Schools Division of Quezon. The research highlighted that these teachers reported high satisfaction levels in areas such as job security, work environment, job responsibilities, and community linkages. Despite these positive aspects, they frequently encountered challenges, including a lack of effective teaching strategies, difficulties with content mastery, and emotional stress. Interestingly, the study found no significant relationship between job satisfaction and performance, suggesting that while individuals are content with certain aspects of their job, these do not necessarily translate into higher performance levels. The find-

ings underscore the importance of addressing the unique challenges faced by non-education graduate teachers to enhance both their satisfaction and effectiveness in the classroom.

Schools in remote regions, particularly in the Tagum North District, lack electricity, which hinders the incorporation of ICT and the availability of technological assistance. A further consideration is the substantial number of students in one room, which necessitates the management of conduct and the preservation of a pleasant, conducive learning environment. Moreover, bureaucratic obstacles, administrative duties, and documentation can exacerbate the stress experienced by teachers in their jobs. Achieving equilibrium between professional obligations and private life can be arduous for educators, resulting in frustration if they perceive themselves as swamped. Supportive coworkers, good school administration, and a positive work atmosphere can enhance job satisfaction and alleviate frustration among non-education degree instructors.

The primary objective of this study was to assess the level of performance of non-education graduate teachers in key areas, including managing insecurities and anxieties, developing content mastery, creating effective teaching strategies, facilitating progress, and employing coping mechanisms. It also aimed to assess their level of job satisfaction in terms of job security, compensation, interrelationships, and organizational culture. Additionally, the study sought to examine whether a significant relationship exists between teacher performance and job satisfaction. Ultimately, the goal was to gather insights and propose a school program that would enhance the performance and job satisfaction of non-education graduate teachers.

The null hypothesis of this study was established and tested at a 0.05 level of significance. It stated that there is no significant relationship between the performance of non-education graduate teachers and their level of job satisfaction.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

The study’s findings benefit key stakeholders by guiding improvements in teaching and policy. The Department of Education can use the results to enhance teacher deployment and curriculum standards. School heads may implement targeted support and training for non-education graduate teachers. Teachers gain insights into their challenges, helping improve classroom practice. Students benefit from more inclusive, engaging learning environments. Future researchers can utilize the findings as a baseline for further studies and policy development.

Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual framework delineating the study’s variables. The input consisted of two primary variables: the

performance of non-education graduate teachers and job satisfaction. The outcome was a planned school program designed to enhance the performance of non-educational graduate teachers and increase job satisfaction in the Tagum North District of Tagum City Division. The study also sought to establish a school program to enhance the performance of non-education degree teachers in the Tagum North District, Tagum City Division. Moreover, a thorough comprehension of the school program designed to enhance the performance of non-education graduates, thereby increasing teacher job satisfaction in Tagum North District, Tagum City Division, is anticipated to result in significant improvements in their teaching efficacy.

2. Methodology

The following section outlines the procedures used by the researcher to perform this research study. It encompasses population and sampling, instrumentation, data sources, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This research used an explanatory sequential mixed-method design, integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches to understand the performance and job satisfaction of non-education degree teachers. First, quantitative data were collected and analyzed using a survey questionnaire. Then, qualitative data from interviews were gathered to explain further and deepen the quan-

titative findings. This two-phase approach allowed the study to capture broad trends and personal experiences, providing a comprehensive view of the factors affecting job satisfaction among non-education graduate teachers (Creswell Creswell, 2023).

2.2. Ethical Considerations—The researcher followed RMC’s ethical guidelines, ensuring informed consent, confidentiality, and

participant safety. The study aimed to enhance job performance and satisfaction among non-education degree teachers, providing policymakers and educators with valuable insights. Vulnerable participants were protected, risks minimized, and academic standards met through expert consultation. Data privacy was maintained, conflicts of interest avoided, and fairness ensured through clear inclusion and withdrawal criteria. Transparency was upheld by briefing participants and openly sharing results, promoting trust and ethical integrity throughout the study.

2.3. Research Respondents—This mixed-methods sequential explanatory study aimed to assess job satisfaction among 90 non-education graduate teachers through a survey and follow-up interviews with five selected participants to deepen the findings. Universal sampling was used to include the entire population, ensuring representative and unbiased results (Creswell Creswell, 2023). The sample size was determined using Tabachnick and Fidell's (2007) formula ($n = 50 + 8m$), which was based on five sub-variables that defined teacher performance. Inclusion criteria required participants to be regular or permanent teachers with over two years of service in the Tagum North District, while those not meeting these conditions were excluded.

2.4. Research Instrument—This study focused on two main variables: the independent variable, which was the performance of non-education graduate teachers measured by five indicators—dealing with insecurities and anxieties, building content mastery, developing teaching strategies and techniques, shaping progress, and coping mechanisms—and the dependent variable, teacher job satisfaction, assessed through four indicators: job security, compensation, interrelationship, and organiza-

tional culture. The study aimed to develop a school program to improve performance and job satisfaction among these teachers in the Tagum North District. A modified survey questionnaire was used, with instruments validated by experts and pilot-tested for reliability. The performance measure was adapted from Patalinghug (2019), and the job satisfaction scale was adopted from Lopes and Oliveira (2020), both of which contain five-item statements for each indicator to ensure a thorough assessment.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—The study adhered to strict ethical and procedural guidelines in both the quantitative and qualitative phases. Permissions and informed consent were obtained before data collection. Experts validated the survey questionnaire, pilot-tested it, and personally distributed it to ensure reliable responses, with data analyzed using SPSS. For the qualitative phase, the interview guide was also expert-validated, and face-to-face interviews were conducted in a confidential, supportive setting, recorded with consent, and analyzed through thematic content analysis and triangulation to provide a comprehensive understanding of participants' experiences.

2.6. Data Analysis—The study used several statistical tools for data analysis: the mean was applied to assess non-education graduate teachers' performance (covering insecurities, content mastery, and teaching strategies) and their job satisfaction (including job security, compensation, relationships, and organizational culture). Pearson's r was used to examine the relationship between teachers' performance and job satisfaction. For qualitative data, Thematic Content Analysis (TCA) was employed to identify key themes from interview transcripts, providing a descriptive insight into participants' experiences (Anderson, 2007).

3. Results

This section presents the results of the data gathered to answer the stated problem of the study. The presentation began with the descriptive analysis of the performance of non-education graduate teachers and job satisfaction, followed by a discussion on the correlation between the two variables. The presentation concluded with a discussion of the themes to determine what school program could be used to raise job satisfaction.

3.1. *Level of performance of non-education graduate teachers*—Table 1 presents the level of performance of non-education graduate teachers, which was assessed using five indicators: dealing with insecurities and anxieties, building content mastery, developing teaching strategies and techniques, shaping progress, and coping mechanisms. The mean ratings for these indicators are as follows: Dealing with Insecurities and Anxieties (2.94), described as moderate; Building Content Mastery (2.80), also

moderate; Developing Teaching Strategies and Techniques (3.51), which was rated high; Being Able to Shape Up Progress (3.45), likewise high; and Coping Mechanism (3.30), rated moderate. These five indicators collectively yielded an overall mean rating of 3.20, indicating a moderate level. This suggests that the performance level of non-education graduate teachers in these key areas is generally moderate, with strengths particularly in teaching strategies and monitoring progress.

Table 1. Level of Performance of Non-Education Graduate Teachers

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	Dealing with insecurities and anxieties	2.94	Moderate
2	Building content mastery	2.80	Moderate
3	Developing teaching strategies and techniques	3.51	High
4	Being able to shape up progress	3.45	High
5	Coping mechanism	3.30	Moderate
Overall		3.20	Moderate

3.2. *Level of job satisfaction of non-education graduate teachers*—Table 2 illustrates the level of job satisfaction among non-education graduate teachers, which was measured using four indicators: job security, compensation, interrelationship, and organizational culture. The mean ratings for these indicators are as follows: Job Security (3.42), described as high; Compensation (3.59), also rated high; Interrelationship

(3.06), interpreted as moderate; and Organization Culture (2.76), which was moderate. The overall mean rating for job satisfaction across these indicators is 3.20, classified as moderate. This suggests that while non-education graduate teachers generally experience high satisfaction in terms of job security and compensation, they also exhibit moderate levels of satisfaction related to their interpersonal relationships and the organizational culture in their workplaces.

3.3. *Significant Relationship between the Performance of non-education Graduates teachers and job satisfaction*—Presented in Table 3

are the results of the test of the relationship between the variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had a computed value r-value

Table 2. Level of Job Satisfaction of Non-Education Graduate Teachers

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	Job security	3.42	High
2	Compensation	3.59	High
3	Interrelationship	3.06	Moderate
4	Organization culture	2.76	Moderate
Overall		3.20	Moderate

of 0.80 with a p-value of 0.002, which is significant at the 0.04 level. This rejects the null hypothesis, stating that there is no significant relationship between the performance of non-education graduate teachers and job satisfaction. This means that as the performance of non-education graduate teachers increases, job satisfaction also increases, or vice versa.

Cohen (2002) states that the calculated r-value of 0.80 signifies a robust positive correlation between the two variables employed to evaluate the hypothesis of a significant relationship. The results clearly indicated a robust

and significant correlation between the performance of non-education graduate teachers and job satisfaction. Consequently, it is expected that anxiety-free second language sessions will result in fewer absences. Having a pairwise correlation among the measures of both variables, it can be gleaned that absences revealed computed values of 0.83 respectively, with p-values which are less than 05 in the level of significance. This implies that as communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, and test anxiety increase, the absences increase.

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between the Performance of Non-Education Graduate Teachers and Job Satisfaction

Variables	r-value	Strength of the Relationship	p-value	Decision
Performance of non-education graduate teachers (x) and job satisfaction (y)	0.83	Very Strong Correlation	.001***	Reject Ho

Note. ***p <.001. A very strong positive correlation was found between performance and job satisfaction.

3.4. *School Program to uplift performance among non-education graduate teachers*—Figure 2 illustrates the school program designed to enhance the performance of non-education grad-

uate teachers, aiming to boost job satisfaction. Four (4) themes were found, namely: (1) self-learning and being resourceful, (2) seeking help, (3) openness and acceptance, and (4) avoiding run-of-the-mill instruction.

4. Discussion

This study aimed to determine the extent of performance of non-education graduate teachers in terms of: dealing with insecurities and anxiety, building content mastery, developing teach-

ing strategies and techniques, shaping progress, and employing coping mechanisms. Further, the study also aimed to determine the extent of job satisfaction in terms of job security, com-

Fig. 2. School Program to uplift the high performance of non-education graduate teachers to boost job satisfaction

pensation, interrelationships, and organizational culture. Additionally, it aims to gather empirical evidence on the perceived relationship between the performance of non-education graduate teachers and their job satisfaction. Furthermore, data were analyzed through thematic content analysis to determine the school program that would uplift the performance of non-education graduate teachers and raise job satisfaction among teachers. The following are the significant findings:

On the extent of performance of non-education graduate teachers. The findings revealed that non-education graduate teachers performed effectively across several areas despite challenges such as limited content mastery and teaching strategies. Their consistent effort, adaptability, and willingness to improve reflect strong personal commitment. This is supported by Bourdieu’s theory, which highlights how individuals navigate professional spaces through alternative forms of capital, and by the Job Characteristics Model, which suggests meaningful work can boost engagement.

On the extent of job satisfaction. Non-education graduate teachers reported high levels of job satisfaction, especially in areas like job security, compensation, and workplace relationships. These positive conditions helped sustain their motivation and performance. Herzberg’s Two-Factor Theory supports this, emphasizing how both supportive environments and recognition enhance satisfaction, while Bourdieu’s

perspective affirms the role of professional acceptance in maintaining morale.

On the results of the test of the relationship between the variables involved in the study. The strong positive correlation between teacher performance and job satisfaction confirms that improvements in one area tend to enhance the other. This finding underscores the importance of supporting both professional effectiveness and well-being. The Job Characteristics Model reinforces this dynamic by showing how enriched roles lead to satisfaction, and Bourdieu’s theory adds that performance can elevate a teacher’s standing within the field.

For the qualitative data. Themes such as self-learning, collaboration, and openness revealed how teachers actively sought ways to improve both their teaching and job satisfaction. These behaviors demonstrate a growth-oriented mindset that contributes to long-term professional success. Herzberg’s theory explains this as motivation driven by intrinsic rewards, while Bourdieu’s concept of capital reflects how these efforts lead to greater acceptance and legitimacy in the teaching profession.

The Department of Education should provide targeted training and ongoing professional development for non-education graduate teachers, with a focus on effective teaching and classroom management. Schools must create supportive and inclusive environments with adequate resources and encourage collaboration. Mentorship programs that pair these teachers

with experienced educators, provide clear performance expectations, offer regular feedback, and offer recognition are essential. Finally, professional learning communities should be established to foster ongoing development, boosting teacher confidence and classroom performance.

5. References

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